

Nanoelectrochemical Platform for Elucidating the Reaction between a Solid Active Material and a Dissolved Redox Species for Mediated Redox-Flow Batteries

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Mediated processes using a solid material, often called “solid booster”, have been proposed to increase the energy density in redox flow batteries (RFB). The strategy alters the energy storage in the dissolved redox species to a solid active material placed in a compartment of the device. Understanding the reaction kinetics of the dissolved redox mediator and the solid booster is crucial for proposing feasible pairs of solid boosters and dissolved redox mediators. We demonstrate a nanoelectrochemical methodology to monitor the reaction between the dissolved species in solution and the solid active material electrodeposited in recessed carbon nanoelectrodes. Our strat-

egy overcomes issues inherent to standard methodologies, such as mass transport limitation, and evaluation of the intrinsic reactivity of the solid material. As a proof of concept, Prussian blue was electrodeposited in a recessed carbon nanoelectrode and used as a confined-solid material platform to evaluate the reaction between the reduced form of Prussian blue and triiodide, I_3^- . A high conversion rate of the solid booster was observed in the presence of μM concentrations of the dissolved redox species. The proposed nanoelectrode was successfully employed as a potentiometric sensor to monitor the evolution of the reaction with the dissolved active species.

Introduction

Redox-flow batteries (RFB) have an advantage of scalability since the power and energy of the energy storage process can be designed separately.^[1] However, this family of technologies possesses limited energy density, compared with conventional solid-based batteries due to the solubility-limited concentration of the dissolved active material. This factor is even more pronounced in aqueous RFB systems due to the voltage limitation caused by water electrolysis and low redox species solubility. Recently, solid materials have been integrated into the flow cell as a strategy to increase the energy density of the rechargeable battery.^[2,3] This powerful strategy was combined with the possibility of confining the solid active material in an external compartment to the redox-mediated flow battery so that power and energy density remain uncoupled.^[2,4,5] The approach is based on the spontaneous thermodynamic reaction between the dissolved species and the solid redox material. The

electrochemical reaction between the dissolved and solid redox materials allows the re-generation of the dissolved species. As a result, the energy density is determined and significantly increased by the solid active material confined in the external reservoirs. In this context, finding candidates of solid material and soluble redox species depends on thermodynamic parameters, such as the redox potentials. The study of the system gains complexity with the reaction reversibility dependence on the state of charge. In this context, tools to evaluate the reaction between the active solid material and soluble species by common techniques are hard due to the limitations in mass transport and slow kinetics.^[5] We show a nanoelectrochemical methodology to monitor the reaction between the solid material and the soluble redox mediator, a crucial evaluation for the development of the mediated redox flow battery technology. Due to the effective mass transfer of the soluble species, using nanoelectrochemistry enabled us to interrogate the spontaneous reaction, avoiding diffusion limitation of the soluble redox species to the solid active surface. Recently, the use of triiodide as a redox mediator was employed in a mediated redox flow battery with Prussian Blue (PB), iron hexacyanoferrate, as a solid material. In this work, the authors pointed out the need to understand the reaction between the soluble and solid active materials to find feasible candidates.^[6] As a proof-of-concept, (PB)/Prussian white (PW) was employed as a solid material confined in a recessed carbon nanoelectrode (rCNE) which allows for the investigation of the intrinsic material performance,^[7] without using an ink or adding a binder. Confining the active material in the tip of the rCNE allowed us to monitor the fast kinetic of the solid material redox process. In other words, using nanoelectrochemistry bypasses the limitations of standard methods once it ensures fast solid material kinetic and hemispherical diffusion of the

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dissolved redox species. As dissolved active species the I_3^-/I^- redox pair was employed to react with PW/PB. The use of triiodide to spontaneously regenerate PB has already been shown to stabilize PB in solar cells^[8] and redox flow batteries.^[9]

Results and Discussion

Functionalization of Recessed Carbon Nanoelectrodes with Prussian Blue

Evaluation of an active material in energy conversion and storage devices by standard techniques leads often to ambiguous interpretations. This is due to the complexity of the systems normally consisting of a mixture of binders, conductive slurries, and a multitude of heterogeneous particles, which makes it difficult to evaluate their intrinsic properties. The use of micro- and nanoelectrodes to study the intrinsic performance of electroactive materials has the advantage of overcoming diffusion limitations and, hence, these type of electrodes were applied in multiple different electrochemical fields e.g. to study electrocatalysts.^[10] We exploit carbon nanoelectrodes as inert electrodes to support electrodeposited PB. The class of PB analogues has been explored in energy storage technology due to their capability of inserting cations, e.g., Na^+ into their structure during the electrochemical reaction.^[11] To confine PB in a rCNE, firstly, a pulled quartz glass nanopipette was filled with carbon produced by pyrolysis of a propane/butane gas mixture employing a fully automatized set-up,^[12] resulting in a carbon nanoelectrode (CNE). More details about automated CNE fabrication method can be found in the experimental section. The obtained CNE tips were cut by focused ion beam (FIB) milling to obtain a well-defined disc-shaped carbon tip. The carbon filling was slightly recessed by exposing the very end of the tip to high temperatures (650°) in air. The depth of the recession can be controlled by the exposure time to high temperature. **Figure S1** resumes SEM images during the fabrication process. After recessing the CNE, PB was electrodeposited by electrochemical reduction of 10 mM $FeCl_3$ and 10 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ from an electrolyte solution containing 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl.^[13] **Figure S2** depicts the typical cyclic voltammetry response for the electrodeposition of PB. To investigate the influence of the PB depth on the electrochemical behavior, PB-modified rCNEs (PB@CNEs) were prepared with different PB deposition depths by varying the heat exposure time (10, 20, and 30 s). The deposition of PB into the cavity of the CNE can be also seen in the element analysis in TEM (**Figure S3**). PB@CNEs were characterized by cyclic voltammetry in aqueous 0.1 M KCl containing 0.1 M HCl (Figure 1). As expected, the resulting PB@CNEs voltammograms revealed the well-known form of the reversible PB/PW reduction and oxidation. The form of the CV and the peak potential separation is indicative of the confined solid material in the cavity, a condition that guarantees a high rate of reversibility of the PB/PW process. Moreover, PB@CNEs prepared with a long exposure time for recessing the CNE are presenting higher currents due to the increased amount of deposited solid material. Note, that a

Figure 1. Cyclic voltammograms for the characterization of PB@CNEs in 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl aqueous solution (scan rate 10 mV s^{-1}) when using a recessed CNE with a heat exposure time of: a) 10, b) 20, and c) 30 s.

precise estimation of the depth of the recession using SEM is difficult due to the minimal difference in contrast between the recessed and not recessed part of the CNE (**Figure S1c**). Interestingly, the electrochemical characterization revealed a trend to much slower kinetics for the PB/PW process when using a long exposure time for recessing the CNEs and thereby forming a deeper recession and PB deposition. As shown in Figure 1, the length of the PB deposits determines the kinetics of the PB/PW electron transfer reaction. A slow ionic and electronic transport occurs at the deeply recessed PB@CNE and diminish the kinetics (Figure 1c). A fast kinetic process is crucial

for the in-situ analysis of a solid booster material, since it is critical to decouple the evaluation of the multiple processes occurring during the reaction between the solid material and the dissolved species. Note, a thicker PB-layer could increase the complexity to evaluate the solid-soluble species reaction once the PB-PW CV exhibited a lower reversibility, as discussed in Figure 1. Therefore, only PB@CNE showing a confined PB-PW CV were employed for such studies. Hence, short-recessed CNEs were used to prepare the PB@CNEs for the following measurements.

Amperometric and Potentiometric Monitoring of the Reaction between the Solid Active Material and Dissolved I_3^-/I^- Species

In a redox-mediated RFB, the regeneration of the redox mediator is based on the spontaneous electron transfer reaction between a solid active material and a soluble redox mediator. Finding suitable candidates for solid booster materials is mainly based on solubility and thermodynamic properties. However, the reaction kinetics between the solid booster material and the soluble redox mediator is another crucial parameter, which needs to be carefully designed.

The majority of corresponding experiments are made in hydrodynamic conditions to ensure fast mass transport.^[5,14] Therefore, using PB@CNEs may circumvent some limitations of

the generally used "standard" methodologies: i) ensure a fast kinetic of the redox process of the solid booster material, ii) allow a hemispherical diffusion of the soluble redox species to the solid material containing nanoelectrode. A PB@CNE was employed as a platform for the converted solid active material, here PW, which was generated by polarizing the nanoelectrode to a reductive potential of +100 mV vs. Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl. Figure 2a exemplifies the reaction principle of the solid material (PB/PW) and the redox species (I_3^-/I^-). The spontaneous conversion of the solid material PW to PB occurs by the reaction with the dissolved redox mediator I_3^-/I^- , due to the potential difference between PW and I_3^- .^[6] Figure 2b shows chronoamperometric sequences registered while polarizing the PB@CNE at +100 mV (vs. Ag/AgCl 3 M KCl) upon adding different amounts of I_3^- in 0.1 M KCl+0.1 M HCl. The current for the PB reduction to PW is measured at the PB@CNE and the monitored reduction current is increasing with the added I_3^- concentration (Figure 2b). The current of PB reduction is due to the regeneration of PB from the reduced PW by the chemical reaction with I_3^- at the PB@CNE interface. The amperometric response of the confined solid material was repeated three times with the same PB@CNE demonstrating high reproducibility (Figure 2c). Interestingly, the calibration curve in Figure 2c depicts two segments. In the low redox mediator concentration range, the diffusion of I_3^- limits PB regeneration. While at higher redox mediator concentrations, the major contribution for the

Figure 2. a) PB@CNE – I_3^- reaction principle. b) Sequence of chronoamperometric curves registered with a PB@CNE polarised at +100 mV vs Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl to promote the reduction of PB to PW while adding I_3^- solution to the electrolyte (0.1 M KCl+0.1 M HCl). Final I_3^- concentrations are indicated at the arrows. c) Calibration curve (modulus of current) registered with a CNE@PB polarised at +100 mV vs Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl to promote the reduction of PB to PW. The initial solution was 0.1 M KCl+0.1 M HCl. d) Stability of the PB@CNE before and after the chronoamperometric measurements. CVs registered in 0.1 M KCl+0.1 M HCl (scan rate: 10 mV s⁻¹).

limit of the reaction rate is the kinetics of the electron transfer between the solid material and the soluble redox species. The diffusion limited current for the I_3^-/PB process can be estimated assuming a disk-shaped PB@CNE, however, not considering the porous characteristics of the PB deposits within the cavity (for more details see the SI). The experimental steady-state currents were substantially lower than predicted suggesting that the active surface area of the PB deposits inside the cavity at which the reaction with I_3^- can occur prevent concluding any diffusion-kinetic limitations. To verify the stability of the PB@CNE after the reaction with the soluble redox mediator, cyclic voltammograms were recorded in 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl in the absence of I_3^- showing an unchanged PB/PW redox process (Figure 2d).

In a control experiment it was investigated if I_3^- reduction is occurring in the selected potential range at a rCNE in the absence of PB deposits.^[15] No faradaic process was registered at the bare CNE in the same potential range upon addition of a comparatively high concentration of 150 mM I_3^- (Figure S4a, SI) confirming that the reduction current in the case of the PB@CNE is solely attributed to the process as depicted in Figure 2a. In contrast to the clear amperometric response recorded at the polarized PB@CNE, a disturbance of the PB/PW process was observed in the CVs recorded upon addition of the redox mediator I_3^- (Figure S4b). As expected, the current of the PB reduction was higher in the presence of the redox mediator, due to the spontaneous regeneration of PW. Simultaneously, a lower current for the electrochemical PW oxidation was observed due to its chemical conversion with I_3^- . These results demonstrated the complexity to derive the reaction rate from the CVs. We hence designed a potentiometric experimental strategy for monitoring the reaction rate by employing the PB@CNE as a sensor. After polarizing the PB@CNE to an initial Nernst potential, the open circuit potential (OCP) is potentiometrically recorded upon addition of different amounts of the soluble redox mediator I_3^- .

In a mediated-redox flow battery, the solid booster material is located in a separate compartment without electrical connection. Hence, the reaction between the solid material and the dissolved redox mediator is occurring spontaneously with the driving force depending on the difference in the state of charge of the solid booster material and the Nernst potential of the dissolved redox mediator. To establish a suitable materials pair with adjusted properties between the solid booster and the dissolved redox mediator is a major challenge.

We employed the PB@CNE as potentiometric sensor, where the open circuit potential (OCP) values change depending on the ratio of PB/PW according to the Nernst equation. Hence, the reaction between the solid material and dissolved redox species was followed by recording the period necessary for achieving the equilibrium OCP at different dissolved I_3^- concentrations. To establish a defined starting OCP, the PB@CNE was polarised at 0 mV for 10 s to convert the PB to PW. After the initial polarisation, the PB@CNE was set to OCP by connecting it as potentiometric sensor to a reference electrode and recording the modulations in the potential values. The OCP values drop from 0 mV (Figure 3) and reach ideally +100 mV, when the PB

Figure 3. a) OCP stabilization of PB@CNE after polarizing at 0 mV for 10 s while adding different amounts of I_3^- between each measurement. Initial solution: 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl. Long period monitoring is presented in the inset graph. b) Slope calculated at the transition time highlighted in a) versus the I_3^- concentration. PB@CNE was employed as a sensor monitoring to estimate the pseudo-first order rate of reaction of PW and I_3^- .

in the PB@CNE is entirely converted to PW. In the presence of a soluble redox species which is capable for the oxidation of PW to PB, the PB/PW ratio changes and the OCP shift accordingly. Figure 3a shows the change of the OCP until the equilibrium open circuit potential was reached after addition of different concentrations of I_3^- .

A slow conversion of PW to PB could be also due to a parasitic reaction with oxygen which is indicated by the black curve in Figure 3a in absence of I_3^- . To evaluate the influence of oxygen, OCP monitoring was repeated in the absence of oxygen and I_3^- , and a stable I_3^- potential was recorded for around 5 h (Figure S5). Note that at this condition, the OCP values had been disturbed by Ar purging, and therefore only the long-term curve was considered. As expected, in the presence of I_3^- , the OCP values increase rapidly reaching a potential which could be correlated to the potential of PB/ I_3^- . The PB@CNE potentiometric response can be correlated to a concentration depending on the reaction rate, and therefore the curves are reflecting the reaction of the solid material with the dissolved I_3^- which is also indicated by the transition between the two potential plateaus at ~0.2 V and ~0.5 V. Hence, the reaction rate could be estimated by monitoring the transition of OCP at different I_3^- concentrations (Figure 3b). The relation between the slope dE/dt and the I_3^- concentration suggests a pseudo-first order rate of

the homogeneous reaction between the solid booster material and the soluble redox mediator. The proposed strategy is capable to follow the reaction occurring spontaneously and compare parameters to be optimized, such as solid material preparation or electrolyte composition.

Conclusions

The confinement of a potential solid booster material in a recessed microelectrode is proposed to interrogate the intrinsic property with respect to electron exchange with a dissolved redox mediator of the solid material, i.e., in absence of a binder and ink formulation. As a proof-of-concept, Prussian-blue was employed as a solid booster material and confined in a recessed carbon nanoelectrode, while the reversible redox species I_3^-/I^- was employed as the dissolved redox couple. Confining the solid material was essential to deconvolute the contribution of the reversibility of the active solid material and the impact of the dissolved redox mediator reaction. The amperometric PB/PW response was sensitive to the presence of μM concentrations to up to 150 mM of dissolved I_3^- demonstrating the spontaneous regeneration mechanism of the dissolved redox species when interacting with the solid booster material (PW to PB regeneration). The potentiometric OCP monitoring was correlated to the rate of spontaneous reaction occurring between the solid material and the dissolved redox mediator. Moreover, the time to reach the final equilibrium OCP values is an indication for the reaction rate between the PW and I_3^- . Elucidating reaction rates is crucial for the development of mediated-redox flow batteries based on the regeneration of the solid material by the dissolved redox species. We hence suggest this nanoelectrochemical methodology to deconvolute the complexity in accessing the reaction between the solid booster and the soluble redox mediator, which we see as a basis for the development of alternative booster and mediator materials for mediated redox flow batteries. In the future such sensors could be integrated within the tank of mediated redox flow batteries to continuously determine the Nernst potential of the dissolved redox mediator and with this the state of charge of the solid booster material.

Experimental Section

Fabrication of Carbon Nanoelectrodes Modified with the Solid Material PB

Carbon nanoelectrodes (CNEs) were prepared utilizing a previously developed fully automated set-up.^[12] Glass pipets were prepared by pulling quartz capillaries (inner diameter: 0.9 mm, outer diameter: 1.2 mm, Sutter Instruments) using a laser puller (P-2000, Sutter Instruments) with the parameters: Heat: 720, Filament: 4, Velocity: 45, Delay: 130 and Pull 100. The automated pyrolysis setup guarantees a controlled filling of carbon into the pipette tip with high reproducibility due to the precise control of heating condition and coil movement. As carbon source, a mixture of butane (99.5%, Air liquide), and propane (technical grade, Air liquide) was used, and a constant gas pressure of 3 bar was applied during pyrolysis.

The argon counter flow (99.999%, Air liquide) was set to 50 mL min⁻¹. Another major parameter is the heating profile of the coil, which was calibrated using a thermocouple prior to the CNE preparation. A two-step temperature profile was used in which the first pyrolysis step was made at 990 °C (pre-pyrolysis). A subsequent second pyrolysis step was performed at a peak temperature of 800 °C followed by a 35 s cooling down phase to 460 °C (post-pyrolysis) to ensure the complete filling of the tip with carbon deposit. To ensure a disc-shaped CNE with a similar opening diameter, pipettes filled with carbon deposits were cut by focused ion beam (FIB) milling. CNEs were electrochemically characterized by cyclic voltammograms in 5 mM $[\text{Ru}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ in 100 mM KCl, resulting in a diffusion-limited steady-state current corresponding to a disk-shaped active surface area with a diameter of around 600 nm, which are in the range of the values observed in the SEM images. The cavity was prepared by locally heating up the tip of the CNE to 650 °C in air and thereby burning away the carbon at the very end of the tip. Prussian blue (PB) was electrodeposited in the rCNE by applying multiple cyclic voltammograms (100 cycles) in 10 mM $\text{FeCl}_3 + 10 \text{ mM } \text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ in an electrolyte containing 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl. The successful deposition of PB within the cavity of the CNE (PB@CNE) was monitored by electrochemical reduction of PB in 0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl. SEM images were obtained to select a cavity depth of around 2 μm , and to verify the presence of PB inside the cavity. STEM images and elemental EDX mappings were performed to characterize the formed PB film before and after the electrochemical experiments in presence of the redox mediator.

Electrochemical Measurements

All electrochemical measurements were performed in a two-electrode configuration using the CNE as the working electrode, and a $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|3 \text{ M KCl}$ as quasi-reference/counter electrode (QRCE). The electrochemical measurements were performed using a low-current potentiostat (Solartron Modulab). The measurements under exclusion of oxygen were performed under continuous argon purging.

Amperometric and Potentiometric Evaluations of PB@CNE

For amperometric analysis, PB@CNE was polarized at +100 mV vs $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|3 \text{ M KCl}$, and a triiodide ion solution was added to the initial electrolyte (0.1 M KCl + 0.1 M HCl). The triiodide ion solution was prepared by preparing a stock solution of iodine/potassium iodide with iodide in excess, and according to the equilibrium the iodine is present as the triiodide ion. Before each OCP monitoring curve, the PB@CNE was polarized for 10 s at +100 mV to convert PB to PW. Subsequently, the cell was switched off and the OCP values were registered.

Supporting Information

The authors have not cited additional references in the Supporting Information.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: mediated redox flow battery · solid active material · redox targeting flow battery · confined electrochemistry · nanoelectrochemistry

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